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FAMILY DISORGANISATION AND CHILDREN

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Abstract

The family is based on and supports primary relations. It provides Very serious especially if the parents don't get along, Insecurity, instability, problems in school, at home, etc. Counseling is always helpful, someone non-biased so the child feels they can trust someone. Children that come from broken families will most likely have a difficult time in life, struggle and turn to drug abuse or other negative behavior. Some kids get made fun of and have no friends. It really brings kids down, when you come home and you see your parents fighting. Children of broken families may go on to have commitment issues. Children from broken families are nearly five times more likely to suffer damaging mental troubles than those whose parents stay together, government research has found. It also showed that two parents are much better than one if children are to avoid slipping into emotional distress and anti-social behavior. The findings say that children's family background are as important - if not more so - than whether their home is poor, workless, have bad health, or has no one with any educational qualifications. Very serious especially if the parents don't get along. Insecurity, instability, problems in school, at home, etc. Counseling is always helpful, someone non-biased so the child feels they can trust someone. Children that come from broken families will most likely have a difficult time in life, struggle and turn to drug abuse or other negative behavior. Getting help may be helpful but it won't help as much. The child can be withdrawn, sad and even act violently towards minor irritations. Each situation is different - but watch for behavioral changes - at home - at school and with friends. A child in this situation needs A LOT of LOVE and EXTRA ATTENTION.

Key Words: Family, Family Disorganisation, Children, Parent-Child Relationship, Single Parental Family

FAMILY DISORGANISATION AND CHILDREN

Family is the most primary and fundamental unit of human society. It is the first to receive the child when it is born. Though almost everybody is born in a family and seems to know and understand what family is from firsthand experience. According to burgers and Locke family is a group of persons united by ties of marriage, blood or adoption. Family according to Mac Aver and Page is a group defined by a sex relationship sufficiently precise and enduring to provide for the procreation and upbringing of children.

Family form varies from society to society. It may be said that family consist of husband and wife and their dependent children. In India joint family joint family system prevails. Even in joint family there is a lot of variation. Some of them are structurally joint others are functionally joint and others are functionally joint and only and few are both structurally and functionally joint. Likewise a family maybe a family without children / will adopted children/ a widow/widower with children / deserted/ divorced woman / man with children.

Family emerged in order to satisfy certain very basic biological, psychological and social needs of man. Family occupies pivotal position in society. Personal and social organization depends upon family organization. The child in its formative years is passive and accepts everything that is given to it by the socializing agents. Thus family plays a lucid role in molding the personality of the child. According to some psychologist a child acquired almost alits personality and character traits of later adulthood before he is of five years of age. These psychological needs are met within the family. It provides him peace, Security, happiness, opportunity to love and be loved etc. All the altruistic attitudes-co-operation, self sacrifice service to humanity, universal brotherhood, love of living beings etc find their origins in family. Family is the most basic and intimate social group. Family being a system of relationships between parents and children. When the psychological factors are absence family becomes disorganized.

During the last several decades, increasing numbers of families have deviated from the traditional model. Divorce forces many children into single-parent families or blended families created by adults living together or remarriage. About 33% of children are born to single mothers, and about 10% of children are born to single teenage mothers. Many children are reared by grandparents or other relatives. Over 1 million children live with adoptive parents. Even traditional families have changed. Often both parents work outside the home,requiring many children to receive regular care outside of the family setting. Because of school and career commitments, many couples postpone having children until their 30s and even 40s. Changing cultural expectations have resulted in fathers spending increasing amounts of time rearing children. Conflicts develop in every family, but healthy families are strong enough to resolve conflicts or thrive despite them. Whatever their makeup, healthy families provide children with a sense of belonging and meet children's physical, emotional, developmental, and spiritual needs. Members of healthy families express emotion and support for each other in ways consistent within their own culture and family traditions.

According to the Statistics of Kerala there has been 350% increase in the divorce over the last decade. The number was 8,456 in 2005-06, 9,775 in 2006-07, 9,937 in 2007-08, 11,196 in 2008-09, 11,600 in 2009-10 and 24,815 in 2010-11and January 2011 and January 2012 the family courts is the state recorded 44,236 cases.

There are many effects on children and adults when families are broken, families can be split apart and sent many miles apart and end up not knowing who they are, or where they belong. There are some effects that are very strong and hurtful, or ones that cannot do anything at all, it all depends on the person and how strong they are. The ones that hurt the most are when you have a strong relationship with one of your siblings or one of your parents and you suddenly get taken away from them. That is something you will never ever be able to get over and move on with in life. Sometimes most people think it's their fault, so it hurts even more. When families are split apart usually everyone goes in separate directions, and usually the whole family looses contact with each other. Those are the effects that hurt the most, especially if your close with them.

Family Disorganization

In its broadest sense, includes any sort of non-harmonious functioning within the family. Thus it may include not only the tensions between husband and wife but these arising between children and parents as well. Parents children tension often present serious problems of adjustment. When the conjugal relationship is broken the

family is then automatically broken. When the reciprocal relationship, the basic of family group, is broken there comes the breakdown in the family organization.

Goode defines family disorganization as the breakup of the family unit. Goode classifies family disorganization into five divisions

1. Illegitimacy: In this type of disorganization role of the father –husband or mother-wife is missing. The source of illegitimacy is to be found in the failure of family members say father and mother to carry out their role obligation.
2. Annulment: Separation, divorce or desertion, in this type of disorganization, one of the couple decide to leave each other, carrying dissolution without discharging their role obligation.
3. Vacuum family: This is the type of family disorganization in which though the spouses live together under the same roof, there is little communication without giving each other much needed emotional support.
4. Unwilled absence of one of the partner: This type of disorganization results when one of the spouses is dead.
5. Unwilled major role failure: This type of disorganization in the result of catastrophe within the family. Catastrophe includes mental, emotional or physical pathologies existing in one or more members in the family.

Divorce, desertion or separations are the final stages of the disorganization process of the family. Divorce is merely the legal recognition given to the break in family relationships.

Factors leading to Family Disorganisations are Parent-Child Relationship, One parental Family, Parents attitude influences the children, Children judge their parents, Family problem

Parent-Child Relationship

Sometimes the children themselves become centre of family tensions and conflicts. Spouses may differ from each other in matters of child s education, type of training descriptive etc. The husband may become jealous of his wife when he thers that his wife gives more attention to children, particularly to the son and he is decent of his wife's affection.

A family in India not only reproductive unit and a socializing agency, it also serves as their link to society. Kinship begins within the family and is extended through the family. “ Family relationship are considered to be the building block of any society, and despite the multitude of changes husband and wife relationship is the sacred duty and religious obligation of the couple to develop and maintain mutual love, care, respect, sacrifice and tolerance within the family environment.(James p.p, Harper and Brothers publishers).

Single Parent Family

In a father absent home, a boy's relationship with the mother will be very different from that of boy who grows up in a family where the father is not only present but also plays an active and dominant rule in family life. When mothers work outside the home and children are cared for by relatives, neighbors or in childcare centers, the relationship of the children with the mother will be very different from that of a children brought up in a home with a home making oriented mother.

How children will react to home influence and how family relationships will affect them will depend on two conditions—what kind of individual the child is and the child's age. The quiet child will react differently from the aggressive child; the introvert will react differently from the extrovert. Second condition, the child's age is also important (*Packman, pp30, child care needs are numbers, Unwed Ltd*). A child grows older peers and other outsiders have increasingly more influence and family members increasingly less.

Parental attitude

Parental attitude influence the way parents treat their children and their treatment of the children, in turn influences their children's attitudes towards them and the way they behave. The effect of broken home on family relationship depend on many factors, the most important of which are the courses of the break, when it occurs, and whether it is temporary or permanent. When a break in the home is caused by death and when children realize that the parent will never return, they mourn the less and transfer their affection to the remaining parent, hoping in this way to reign the security they formerly had.

In early life loss of the mother is more damaging than loss of the father. The reason for this is that care of young children must under the circumstances, be turned over to relatives or paid housekeepers whose child-training techniques may differ from those used by the mothers and who rarely can give children the attention and affection they formerly received from their mothers.

Children Judge their Parents

As English writer Oscar Wild said, "Children begin by loving their parents; after a time they judge them, rarely if ever, do they forgive them." Parents are human as it is only natural to make mistakes. There are common mistakes parents make and tips to avoid them

Promising expensive gifts and treats to substitute for time spent away from the child is also a bad idea. It is impossible to learn to ride a bicycle if someone is constantly holding you from behind. Falls and bruises are part of the process. As a part, your job is not make the ride easy, but to ensure that the child is tough enough to get up after every fall you aren't always going to be around to protect him. The parents are the sole decision makers. The steering wheel, gear breaks even the music system is under the control. Obedience is paramount and disciplinary measures severe.

Family Problem

Every family has family problems but there are certain measures can take for recovery. Personalities, Clash and power struggles ensure as parents and children learn how to identify how to cope with each other. Family meeting provides a safe environment for each member to share their views o various issues.

Conclusion

Family breakdown is not a single event, but a process that involves a number of risk and protective factors that interact in complex ways both before and after parental separation or divorce to increase or limit the risk of the adverse outcomes associated with family breakdown. These inter-related factors include parental conflict; the quality of parenting and of parent-child relationships; maternal mental health; financial hardship; and repeated changes in living arrangements, including family structure. Parental conflict is a key variable associated with negative outcomes in children from both intact and non-intact families. Research in this area clearly shows that

family functioning has a greater impact on outcomes than family structure. High levels of conflict, stress resulting from the separation and/or resulting poverty can all negatively affect maternal mental health.

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